

Certification of Natural Pasture Meat in Finland

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Grazing cattle in Finland (Photo: Tanja Kähkönen).

Labelling and certification can show consumers reliability of agroforestry products. In Finland, many natural or semi-natural pastures—especially traditional rural biotopes like wood pastures and meadows—are examples of agroforestry systems. Certification of natural pasture meat has entered from Sweden to Finland. In Finland, *Sigill Luonnonlaidun* (*Sigill Natural Pasture*) label in meat indicates that labelled meat originates in animals which have grazed Finnish meadows and natural pastures. This label also indicates that requirements for food safety, animal wellbeing and environmental responsibility are met. Essentially the label indicates that the Finnish farm has an environmental certification according to the requirements of *IP Sigill* quality system. Certification rules have been developed together by a company, *Sigill Kvalitetssystem AB* in Sweden, and *World Wildlife Fund*. In Finland the certification of *Sigill Kvalitetssystem* is endorsed by *Kvalitet från Finland* Ab.

The most important criteria in the label are 1) animals graze on natural pastures for at least 50% of the grazing period and 2) cattle over 250 kg is fed with at least 70% roughage during the housing period. Farms which have natural pasture meat certification are inspected every two years by independent accredited bodies. Auditing fees varied between 290 e to 1090 e in year 2023 depending on the number of slaughtered/sold animals per year and an annual fee paid to the representative organization of *Sigill Kvalitetssystem Ab* in Finland. There is an own label both for cattle and sheep natural pasture meat. From business perspective, certification can for instance support in expanding markets for products, in showcasing environmental and sustainability efforts of the farm in a reliable way, and in establishing trust between producers and customers. Certification can be beneficial especially for farmers who are interested in improving environmental sustainability of their farm and get official certification for it.

In Finland, *Luonnonlaidunlihan tuottajat ry* (Natural pasture meat producers registered association) has been established in year 2020 to bring together natural pasture meat producers in Finland.

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